

ISSN: 2005-4238

International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology

IJAST

Science & Engineering
Research Support soCietY

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF THE GLAUTESX DRAINAGEIMPLANTATION TECHNIQUE IN SURGICAL TREATMENT OF CONGENITALGLAUCOMA

Zulfiya Nazirova, DilfuzaTurakulova, Lola Babadjanova
Tashkent pediatric medical institute, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Abstract

The results of 17 antiglaucomatous operations with Glautex drainage implantations are analyzed. The age of patients ranged from 10 days to 3 years. The average age was 18.2 ± 0.3 months. Boys made up 9 (52.8%) while girls constituted 8 (47.2%). All patients had previously undergone antiglaucomatous surgery, of which in 10 of them -onlyonce, 5 patients went under knife twice and in 2 cases - three times. When conducting anti-glaucomatous operations using Glautex drainage, it is necessary to follow some technical nuances to prevent intra- and postoperative complications.

Keywords---antiglaucomatous operation, congenital glaucoma, biodegradable drainage Glautex.

Relevance

Congenital glaucoma is one of the main causes of blindness and low vision in children, which in the structure of eye pathology reaches up to 0.1%. Children with glaucoma compose 5 to 15% among students in specialized schools of blind and visually impaired [1,2,3].

Primary congenital glaucoma (PCG) is manifested at an early age of a child under 3 years old. It has a recessive type of inheritance, although sporadic cases are also possible. The pathogenesis mechanism of ophthalmic hypertension and congenital glaucoma as a whole is associated with an interruption of the outflow of aqueous humor from the anterior chamber of the eye to the scleral sinus, due to congenital anomalies in the structure of the anterior chamber angle.

The main treatment for children with congenital glaucoma is surgical treatment. Due to the anatomical and physiological characteristics of the eyeball in children, any ongoing anti-glaucomatous interventions are often less effective than in adults. This is due to the growth of the eyeball, which has its own characteristics in childhood.

The effectiveness of antiglaucomatous operations ranges from 92.3% in the early postoperative period to 46% in the long term. It is also noted that each subsequent operation is associated with a risk of new complications, and its effectiveness is reduced by 2-3 times. Many authors note that a high antihypertensive effect persists during the first year of life to 80-95%, later these indicators begin to decline to 45%, and therefore an early antiglaucomatous operation is the optimal method of treatment. For many years goniotomy has been the most common among antiglaucomatous operations. It is based on the dissection with a knife - a goniotome - of the mesodermal tissue which covers the trabeculae, that opens up access to aqueous humor to the drainage paths. But this method of surgical treatment is effective only with true congenital glaucoma, surgery is impossible if the visualization of the iris-corneal angle is difficult. Special equipment is required and there is a risk of damaging the corneal endothelium, structures of the iris-corneal angle and lens. One of the methods of surgical access to the sinus from the outside is *abexternotrabeculotomy*, which is based for the creation of direct communication between the anterior chamber and the venous sinus of the sclera [4,5]. At the same time, the conjunctiva and Tenon's capsule are involved in the intervention, which leads to their subsequent scarring and creates difficulties for creating a filtering bleb during subsequent "filtering" operations; there is no clear visualization of the iris-corneal angle, which can potentially lead to damaging of various structures of the eyeball and result in low-effect-operation. Given the fact that with congenital glaucoma in 4-20% of cases the Schlemm canal is absent, with its sounding is accordingly not always possible. Persistent hypotension of the eyeball after surgery is possible.

One of the ways to increase the effectiveness of fistulizing operations aimed at the long-term preservation of the hypotensive effect is the use of drains [6,7,8,9,10,11,12]. Drainage devices for

glaucoma in children are reserved for refractory cases of PCG, when trabeculectomy does not work or is not applicable. The surgical technique is the same as in adults, although there are children's models for almost all drainage devices. The effectiveness after surgery is 44% - 95% and 60% - 65% during two-year examinations, respectively. Complications after drainage surgery are the same as in adults and include tube-related complications (corneal contact, implant exposure, tube blockage, dislocation), eye movement disorders and infection.

Thus, the results obtained indicate the promise of the use of drainages in the treatment of congenital glaucoma, especially as repeated operations [13,14, 15].

Purpose of the study

Studying the features of surgery during implantation of Glautex drainage to prevent intra- and postoperative complications in anti-glaucomatous surgery in children.

Materials and research methods

We examined and operated on 17 (34 eyes) children who are hospitalized in the eye department of the clinic of Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute with primary congenital glaucoma. The study did not include children with secondary, combined glaucoma and children with systemic diseases. The age of patients ranged from 10 days to 3 years. The average age was 18.2 ± 0.3 months. Boys made up 9 (52.8%) while the opposite gender made up 8 (47.2%). All children were hospitalized on an emergency basis. Following the preoperative preparation, they underwent antiglaucomatous surgery. For patients under 1 month of age, preparation for surgical treatment was carried out in the intensive care unit. The following research methods were used on patients: gonioscopy using a Goldman lens, Maklakov's tonometry, tonography (according to Fridenwald tables) and ultrasound A, B scanning of the eyeball, bio-microscopy. On the ultrasonic equipment STRONG 6000 + T and on the machine of ALCON REXP ocular scan, the anterior - posterior axis of the eyeball was determined.

The data obtained during the study were subjected to statistical processing on a personal computer using the Microsoft Office Excel-2010 software package, including the use of built-in statistical processing functions.

Results

We performed operations on 17 patients who underwent antiglaucomatous surgery: sinus-trabeculotomy using biodegradable drainage Glautex. All patients had previously undergone antiglaucomatous surgery, of which 10 patients – only once, in 5 patients - twice and only 3 operations were performed in 2 cases. True intraocular pressure before surgery on the drug regimen ranged from 29.0 to 35.0 mm Hg. and averaged 32.4 ± 0.8 mm Hg.

According to A-scan data, the average anterior-posterior axis was 28.6 ± 0.7 mm. During B-scanning, single floating opacities were observed in all patients in the vitreous body, the retina was adhering.

Gonioscopy was carried out in patients under anesthesia, while the second degree of goniodysgenesis — high attachment of the iris root at the level of the posterior third of the abnormal trabeculae — was observed in 34.6% of cases. The space between the root of the iris and the anterior Schwalbe border ring was noted, filled with a semi-translucent grayish tissue or a continuous layer of mesodermal tissue in the form of a Barkan membrane. Of these, in 5.6% of cases, in the area of the trabecula, the crest ligaments formed a “jagged” line. The third degree of goniodysgenesis was observed in 13.1% of cases and was characterized by the fact that the root of the iris was located at the level of the middle of the trabeculae, in 10% the atypical position and obliteration of the Schlemm's canal. In 44% of children, gonioscopy was not possible due to severe edema and clouding of the cornea.

All children underwent anti-glaucomatous surgery. 7-10 days before surgery, drugs that reduce intraocular pressure are canceled. Three days before the operation, antibacterial eye drops were prescribed to prevent secondary infection.

Glautex biodegradable drainage characteristics: it is a white porous bioresorbable film with a good filtering effect; made from a composition based on polylactic acid (polylactide) and polyethylene glycol; has the shape of a rectangular coupling (closed ring) $2.8 \times 2.0 \times 0.15$ mm when folded with a thickness of 80 μm , pore diameter 30-50 μm . (model TMA). Does not swell, does not make excessive pressure on the surrounding tissue; terms of complete resorption are around 4–5 months.

When performing trabeculotomy, we were located at the operating table, depending on the location of the expected incision area. It is important to preserve the conjunctiva for possible future anti-glaucomatous operations. We prefer temporal access, which helps to prevent application of the frenulum suture. A traction suture can be applied to the cornea away from the site of surgery, so that pulling the thread, you can examine the entire quadrant of the proposed intervention.

After a 5 mm long incision of the conjunctiva, a scleral flap is cut out along the limb and it is thrown back onto the cornea. The shape of the flap is selected based on our preferences, we prefer a trapezium-shaped flap 3x3mm., About half or two thirds of the thickness of the sclera. A coagulator was used to provide hemostasis; the procedure is performed with a light touch so as not to cause excessive tissue contraction. Then a blade with an angle of inclination of 15 degrees perform a radial incision of 1.5-2.0 mm in the bed of the scleral flap. The incision should be made in front of the posterior edge of the limb. At the opening of the Schlemm's channel, aqueous humor may leak. A change in the course of the scleral fibers in a perpendicular direction with respect to the limb with the appearance of light ripples in the wound locus indicates the position of the Schlemm's canal. The Schlemm's canal is located anterior to the intermediate zone, where the gray-blue surgical limb passes into the white circular fibers of the sclera. These fibers correspond to the position of the scleral spur; the Schlemm's canal is usually located anterior to it. When performing the cut, the blade with an angle of inclination of 15 degrees should pass horizontally, slightly raising the fabric so that the cut is not too deep, thereby excluding the opening of the front camera.

As soon as the position of the Schlemm's channel is determined, a metal trabeculotome is inserted into the inlet to the right or left of the opened Schlemm's channel. It is much easier to determine the position of the Schlemm's channel by introducing 6/0 polypropylene thread into it, and then confirm its location under the control of the gonioscope. To do this, polypropylene yarn 6 \ 0 with a length of approximately 65-80 mm in the form of a fishing hook is used. Using a high-temperature coagulator, the short end of the thread is cauterized to form a small round head, similar to a mushroom cap. The introduction of such a rounded end of polypropylene yarn 6 \ 0 into the inlet indicates that it is in the Schlemm's channel. The thread should move easily, without significant resistance. If the thread begins to bend, it is removed and inserted again. If the thread is difficult to move into the hole, an additional cut is made with a blade with an inclination angle of 15 degrees to expand it. As soon as a part of the thread has entered the hole, it is advanced further by approximately 5-10 mm. You must make sure that the thread is not in the anterior chamber and that it is visible inside the angle structures of the anterior chamber.

If the thread is invisible with a sufficient visualization of the angle of the anterior chamber, then this may be due to either too front attachment of the iris, or to the thread being in the suprachoroidal space. If there is such suspicion or the front camera has become shallow, we introduce a viscoelastic.

If it is impossible or difficult to visualize the thread during gonioscopy, its exact location can be determined by external examination: the guiding thread should go parallel to the limb, while the front camera should not be too small. Then it is needed to slightly pull the protruding part of the thread first towards the cornea and then in the opposite direction, making sure of the resistance of the thread when shifting in both directions.

Before the introduction of the metal trabeculotome into the Schlemm's canal, paracentesis is performed and carbachol is injected into the anterior chamber. Carbachol, pulling the iris from the corner of the anterior chamber and creating myosis, closes the lens surface with the iris as much as possible, protecting it from possible damage during trabeculotomy, and also prevents iris prolapse. Then we deepen the anterior chamber with viscoelastic for additional protection of the eye structures.

The lower end of the right or left trabeculotome is carefully inserted into the Schlemm's canal, as much as the curvature of the probe allows. It can be difficult to introduce a trabeculotome into the channel along its entire length, however, it is advisable to introduce a tool of 2/3 of the channel length. As the trabeculotome has maximally entered the Schlemm's channel, it is turned towards the anterior chamber with a rotating movement between the thumb and forefinger. You should make sure that the trabeculotome does not turn in the direction of the cornea and does not cause detachment of the Descemet's membrane. It is also necessary to ensure that the trabeculotome is not pulled by the iris and does not stimulate iridodialysis or damage the lens. If the trabeculotome is under the sheet of the iris, all manipulations should be stopped immediately, as in the case of insertion of the trabeculotome into the suprachoroid space.

After performing a trabeculotomy on both sides, we carefully remove the trabeculotome, avoiding damage to the iris and its loss into the surgical incision.

In case of prolapse, the iris can be successfully repaired by making a small iridotomy.

After that, we put on the drainage sleeve on the scleral flap. Then the scleral flap with the drainage put on it is laid in place, repositioned and fixed with 1 or 2 sutures in the apex region. The conjunctival incision is sutured with a nodal suture. Following technical nuances must be taken into account while performing this type of surgery:

1. Cut the scleral flap at the place where no surgical intervention had previously been performed, since sclera thinning is noted at the previously performed site, which in turn leads to difficulties in the formation of the flap, as the latter becomes very thin and can break quickly;

2. When forming a scleral flap, it is necessary to clearly determine the width of the flap using a compass in advance. Width should be 3.0 mm. and length - 3.0 mm. With a flap width of more than 3.0 mm, difficulties will arise when putting on GlauTex drainage. In case of a smaller width while putting on the drainage, it is not fixed, it hangs and the tongue that should be in the front chamber pops out of it. With a long flap, difficulties arise when putting on drainage and controlling the tongue in the anterior chamber, with a short flap of less than 3.0 mm, difficulties emerge when sewing the scleral flap to the sclera and when fixing the flap.

3. When cutting a flap, its size is reduced, which must be taken into account when forming it.

After anti-glaucomatous operation is performed, the postoperative period was reactive. During biomicroscopy, GlauTex drainage was visualized as a rectangle. The level of true IOP (Po) after surgery decreased by 47% and averaged 11.1 mm Hg., hypotension was noted for 3-5 days in 3 (17.6%) children. Also, in 2 (11.7%) children, choroid detachment was marked. Hypotension in patients was stopped on days 7-8 by administration of Atropine eye drops (2 drops twice a day) and Caffeine (2 drops 6 times a day). In the main group, moderate hypotension was detected in 3 patients on day 2 and stopped on day 5 after administration of Caffeine.

Thus, a preliminary analysis of the surgical treatment of children with congenital glaucoma with the use of GlauTex drainage showed that the use of GlauTex drainage makes it possible to achieve a persistent hypotensive effect and provides prevention of the occurrence of sclera-conjunctival, sclera-scleral adhesions.

The location of the drainage around the scleral flap in the form of a "sleeve" eliminates the possibility of its dislocation and provides prevention of the occurrence of sclera-conjunctival, sclera-scleral adhesions, as well as adhesions along the edge of the scleral flap. In addition, the use of drainage does not complicate the course of operations; its installation does not require complex and time-consuming manipulations.

After surgical treatment, children under one year of age were in the intensive care unit under the supervision of an anesthesiologist on the first day, children older than one year of age were transferred into the postoperative ward in the ophthalmic department.

After surgical treatment, children were hospitalized for an average of 5-7 days ($6.1 \pm$ bed days). All children with satisfactory health condition were discharged home with later plans for supervision of an ophthalmologist at the place of residence.

Conclusions.

When conducting anti-glaucomatous operations using Glautex drainage, it is necessary to observe some technical nuances to prevent intra- and postoperative complications. Glautex drainage implantation makes it possible to obtain a persistent hypotensive effect, but at the same time prevents excessive filtration of intraocular fluid along the newly formed outflow pathways, which is a kind of prevention of postoperative hypotension and, as a result, of choroid detachment. All of the above can reduce the likelihood of repeated surgical interventions.

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